

1 **Built structures strongly influence cross-country patterns of energy demand** 2 **and CO₂ emissions**

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16 **Built structures, i.e. the patterns of settlements and transport infrastructures, are**
17 **known to influence per-capita energy demand and CO₂ emissions at the urban level¹⁻⁵.**
18 **At the national level, other potential determinants of energy demand and CO₂ emissions,**
19 **primarily GDP, have received much attention⁶⁻⁸, but the role of built structures has so**
20 **far been disregarded due to lacking data. We present a set of novel national-level**
21 **indicators derived from global satellite- and crowd-sourced maps to characterize extent**
22 **and spatial patterns of built structures. We quantify these indicators for 113 countries**
23 **and statistically analyze the results along with final energy use and territorial CO₂**
24 **emissions, as well as conventional factors thought to drive energy use and emissions. We**
25 **find that our indicators are about equally important for predicting energy demand and**
26 **CO₂ emissions as GDP and other conventional factors. The area of built-up land per**
27 **capita is the most important predictor, second only to the effect of GDP. We conclude**
28 **that the extent and spatial layout of built structures strongly affects energy demand and**
29 **emissions. Reducing land take of built structures and altering their patterns emerges as**
30 **an under-appreciated option for sustainability-oriented strategies.**

31

32 **Main**

33 Rapidly progressing climate heating driven by growing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is a
34 major concern⁹. GHGs mainly result from energy-related combustion of fossil fuels¹⁰. The

35 question emerges, which factors drive energy demand and emissions, and to what extent their
36 trajectories can be altered. This question is relevant at many levels, from products to
37 individuals, households, cities up to continental and even global totals. We here focus on
38 countries, because many decision-making processes occur at the national level. A widespread
39 approach for cross-country analyses classifies the factors driving resource use and emissions
40 into population, affluence and technology¹¹⁻¹³. These drivers are captured in the STIRPAT
41 (Stochastic Impacts by Regression on Population, Affluence and Technology) framework¹¹,
42 derived from the classical IPAT (impact = population x affluence x technology) approach^{13,14}.

43

44 Economic activity ('affluence' in IPAT-style analyses, usually measured as Gross Domestic
45 Product or GDP) is acknowledged as a major driver of energy use and greenhouse gas (GHG)
46 emissions⁶⁻⁸. The discussion mainly focuses on whether GDP can be 'decoupled' from
47 emissions, i.e., whether energy use and emissions can be reduced while GDP is growing. This
48 may be possible e.g. through more efficient technologies, but the debate is so far
49 inconclusive^{15,16}. While recent studies revealed examples of growing national economies
50 where policies implemented in the last decade achieved reductions in energy demand and CO₂
51 emissions¹⁷⁻¹⁹, neither those studies nor a meta-analysis²⁰ yielded evidence for reductions in
52 energy use and GHG emissions consistent with ambitious climate targets.

53

54 Other potential drivers of energy demand and emissions received less attention than GDP.
55 Population density has been studied with varied outcomes. An econometric study of OECD
56 countries 1980-2011 suggested an inverse relation between population density and CO₂
57 emissions²¹; a regression analysis of materials use in >100 countries in 2000 found a similar
58 effect²². A global regression analysis²³ found no effect of population density on energy
59 demand, whereas a panel analysis of 11 Asian countries 1960-2004²⁴ revealed a positive
60 relation between CO₂ emissions and population density. Relevant factors also include climatic
61 conditions that drive energy demand for heating or cooling of buildings²⁵, fuel prices affecting
62 demand for transport energy²⁶, and the urbanization rate (urban population as percent of total
63 population).

64

65 At the urban scale, the influence of population density and the spatial layout of urban areas on
66 cities' resource demand has been widely studied^{1-4,25,27,28}. There are several reasons why the
67 extent and spatial layout (density and form) of built structures – henceforth denoted as
68 'material stock patterns'²⁹, i.e. the spatial patterns of society's material stocks in

69 infrastructures and buildings – should affect energy demand and CO₂ emissions. The
70 accumulation of material stocks requires massive amounts of resources such as steel-
71 reinforced concrete, mortar, bricks, timber, plastics, glass, gravel or sand³⁰⁻³³, which are
72 associated with high GHG emissions³⁴. Heating, cooling and lighting of buildings and
73 production processes in industrial plants require much energy^{1,4,25,35}, as does mobility of
74 goods and people on roads and railways^{33,36}.

75
76 Despite these insights from urban studies, material stock patterns are largely ignored in
77 debates on national-level analyses of factors determining levels of energy demand and
78 emissions, as well as their possible decoupling from GDP^{16,20}. A systematic review of the
79 empirical literature on these questions^{20,37} revealed only one study³⁸ considering material
80 stock patterns in analyzing transport-related emissions. Hence little is known on the effects of
81 material stock patterns on energy demand and CO₂ emissions beyond the city level. This
82 results from a scale mismatch: maps of material stock patterns provide fine-grained spatial
83 detail³⁰, often focused on specific regions, that cannot be included in national-level analyses
84 of factors driving energy demand and emissions. For cross-country analyses, consistent
85 indicators need to be developed from spatial data and then aggregated to the national level in
86 a manner which preserves key information on patterns and supports comparative analyses
87 across countries and world-regions.

88
89 To address this research gap, we developed national-level indicators of material stock patterns
90 focused on features of built structures that, based on urban studies, might be potential
91 determinants of resource use and emissions (Figure 1). We calculated the indicators presented
92 in Table 1 for 113 countries comprising 91.2% of the world population and 97.3% of global
93 GDP. Yearly total per-capita final energy consumption (abbreviated as TFC) was used as
94 energy demand indicator, complemented by yearly per-capita CO₂ emissions (abbreviated as
95 CO₂). We then tested material stock pattern indicators against other potential determinants of
96 TFC and CO₂, in the following text denoted as ‘conventional factors’. We assembled a cross-
97 country dataset of conventional factors that includes economic activity (GDP/cap/yr,
98 abbreviated GDP), population density (DENS), as well as urban population as percent of total
99 population (UPOP) as development indicator³⁹. To capture climatic factors, we used heating-
100 degree days (HDD) as a proxy of climate dependency of energy demand²⁵. Because economic
101 activities are influenced by prices, we included the price of gasoline (PGAS) as an energy
102 price indicator that has been shown to be strongly related with settlement patterns²⁶. Extensive

103 variables were expressed as per-capita values to facilitate country comparisons and remove
104 countries' population numbers from the analysis.

105

106 **Results**

107 **National-level indicators of material stock patterns**

108 We tested three hypotheses based on aggregated indicators of material stock patterns (Figure
109 1), represented by three types of indicators: (1) The area of built-up land is represented by two
110 indicators, one as fraction of a nation's inhabited land, the other per inhabitant. Other
111 indicators describe patterns of built-up areas, including their spatial clustering, form and
112 distribution, which reflect geomorphological factors as well as historical contingencies. (2)
113 Road indicators that describe the density (length per unit area) of roads in urban and rural
114 regions and the relations between urban and rural road lengths and densities. (3) Railway
115 indicators were defined in the same manner as those for roads (Table 1).

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Figure 1. Workflow of this study. National-level indicators of the extent and spatial patterns of settlements and infrastructures (‘material stock patterns’) were derived from global maps, here illustrated using Paraguay, the UK, Kenya and Bangladesh as examples. Results were statistically analyzed along with the conventional factors assumed to co-determine energy use and CO₂ emissions. The main aim was to test the hypotheses formulated in the lower-right box.

124 **Table 1. Indicators of the extent and patterns of built-up land and transport infrastructures.** These
 125 indicators condense spatially explicit information in maps to national-level indicator values assumed to co-
 126 determine a nation's per-capita level of energy demand and CO₂ emissions. Global maps showing the indicator
 127 values are in Extended Data Figures 5-7.

Name	Abbreviation	Description and interpretation	Unit
(1) Indicators for the extent and pattern of a nation's built-up land			
Fraction of built-up land	BL _{fract}	Built-up land (buildings & infrastructures) as % of the inhabited land area.	m ² /m ²
Built-up land per capita	BL _{cap}	Built-up land per capita.	m ² /cap
Dispersion of built-up land	BL _{disp}	Index based on the average distance of each patch of built-up land to the nearest adjacent patch. High values indicate strong dispersion.	--
Monocentricity of built-up land	BL _{mono}	Area of the largest contiguous built-up patch as % of the sum of the areas of the ten largest patches. High values indicate dominance of one large center.	m ² /m ²
Compactness of built-up land	BL _{comp}	Index describing how 'round' or 'compact' the shapes of a nation's built-up land patches are on average.	--
Urban population density	UP _{dens}	Urban population per unit of urban built-up land	cap/m ²
(2) Indicators of road density and distribution			
Road density	RD _{total}	Length of roads per unit area of inhabited land.	m/m ²
Urban road density	RD _{urban}	Length of roads in urban areas per unit area of urban areas.	m/m ²
Rural road density	RD _{rural}	Length of roads in rural areas per unit area of rural areas; proxy of rural accessibility and connectivity between urban centers.	m/m ²
Ratio of urban-to-rural road lengths	RL _{urb-rur}	Ratio of urban to rural road lengths, indicating the extent to which roads are concentrated in cities.	--
Ratio of urban-to-rural road density	RD _{urb-rur}	Ratio of RD _{urban} and RD _{rural} , indicating the difference between urban and rural road densities.	--
(3) Indicators of railway density and distribution			
Railway density	RWD _{total}	Length of railways per unit area of inhabited land.	m/m ²
Urban railway density	RWD _{urban}	Length of railways in urban areas per unit area of urban areas.	m/m ²
Rural railway density	RWD _{rural}	As RD _{rural} for railways.	m/m ²
Ratio of urban-to-rural railway lengths	RWL _{urb-rur}	As RL _{urb-rur} for railways.	--
Ratio of urban-to-rural railway density	RWD _{urb-rur}	As RD _{urb-rur} for railways.	--

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129 **Bivariate and semi-partial correlations**

130 In terms of their Pearson coefficients in bivariate correlations, several indicators of material
 131 stock patterns are as strongly correlated with TFC and CO₂ as the conventional factors (Figure
 132 2a). GDP is positively correlated with both TFC and CO₂. HDD and the fraction of urban
 133 population also show the expected pattern, while PGAS and DENS are largely uncorrelated.
 134 Almost all material stock pattern indicators are correlated with both TFC and CO₂. The extent
 135 of built-up land (BL_{cap} and BL_{fract}) is positively correlated with both TFC and CO₂, as are total
 136 and rural road density and the dispersion of built-up land and most railway-related indicators.
 137 The correlation coefficients of BL_{cap} with TFC and CO₂ are both ~0.7; BL_{cap} is the second-
 138 best predictor of both TFC and CO₂ after GDP. As expected from the urban literature, urban
 139 population density (UP_{dens}) is inversely correlated with CO₂ and energy, whereas the share of

140 urban population (UPOP) is strongly positively correlated with CO₂ and TFC. Inverse
141 relations prevail for BL_{mono}, BL_{comp} and the urban-to-rural relations of infrastructure density.
142

143 Semi-partial correlations of the material stock pattern indicators controlled for GDP and
144 population density (DENS) are shown in Figure 2b. The part of each material stock pattern
145 indicator correlated with GDP and DENS is removed, revealing the strength of the linear
146 correlation between TFC or CO₂ and the remaining part of the respective variable. The
147 distance from the vertical axis either to the right (positive correlation) or to the left (inverse
148 correlation) depicts the additional explanatory power of the respective indicator over a model
149 considering only GDP and DENS. Several indicators provide additional explanations over
150 GDP and DENS alone. The area of built-up land (both BL_{cap} and BL_{fract}) is positively
151 correlated with TFC and CO₂, as are the density of rail and road infrastructures, especially in
152 rural areas. UPOP is inversely correlated with TFC and CO₂, as is urban road density (not
153 significant) and BL_{mono}. PGAS, which had not been significant in the bivariate correlations,
154 emerges as an important factor, which is also observed for RD_{urban} and other indicators. UP_{dens}
155 loses importance, most likely due to its high correlation with GDP.

156 (a)

157 (b)
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161 **Figure 2. Correlation analyses of total final energy demand per capita (TFC) and per-**
 162 **capita CO₂ emissions (CO₂) with conventional factors and material stock**
 163 **indicators. (a) Pearson’s zero correlation coefficients of correlations between TFC (left) and**
 164 **CO₂ (right) and material stock pattern indicators as well as conventional factors. Natural**
 165 **logarithms of the variables were analyzed. Squaring the correlation coefficients gives the**
 166 **percentage of the cross-country variation of CO₂ or TFC explained by the respective indicator**
 167 **alone. Asterisks: not significant (p<0.1). (b) Semi-partial correlations between material stock**
 168 **pattern indicators and TFC (left) and CO₂ (right) controlling for GDP and DENS. Distance**
 169 **from the vertical axis indicates the correlation coefficient of the semi-partial correlation, and**
 170 **distance from the horizontal axis is the correlation coefficient of the bivariate (uncontrolled)**
 171 **correlation. Red contours indicate insignificant results (significance level p<0.1).**
 172

173 **Multivariate lasso analysis**

174 The capability of the material stock pattern indicators to add insights beyond conventional
 175 factors is further analyzed in Table 2. We used the ‘least absolute shrinkage and selection

176 operator' (lasso) approach to select variables for multivariate statistical models capable of
177 predicting cross-country patterns of TFC and CO₂. Lasso is a standard regularization
178 technique for model selection and prediction that penalizes complexity to derive the best
179 parsimonious model for any predefined value of λ (the factor determining how strongly model
180 complexity is penalized; for detail see Methods section). Randomly chosen samples of
181 countries are used to develop a model used for prediction of patterns in 'out-of-sample'
182 countries. The procedure gradually reduces λ , which generally results in more indicators
183 being selected.

184
185 The leftmost three columns of Table 2 show the knots in the lasso paths, i.e. the λ values at
186 which indicators are added (or removed due to collinearity). Knots are arranged in decreasing
187 order of λ , with indicators being ranked in order of selection. In the first column, λ^* marks the
188 optimal model identified by the cross-validation. GDP is always selected as first indicator, but
189 various material stock pattern indicators appear very early on (i.e. at high λ values), and
190 remain active in the optimal model. BL_{cap} is the second-chosen indicator for both CO₂ and
191 TFC, and several other material stock pattern indicators are selected much earlier than widely-
192 used conventional factors such as population density (DENS). Heating-degree days (HDD)
193 and price of gas (PGAS) are important for both CO₂ and TFC, whereas UPOP is important for
194 predicting CO₂ but not selected by lasso for TFC.

195
196 The rightmost three columns of Table 2 report the estimated coefficients of models selected
197 by cross-validation as well as measures of in-sample and out-of-sample fit (r^2). Models A
198 comprise only variables selected by lasso (path shown in the left part of the table) among all
199 indicators. For the benchmark Models B, only conventional factors were selected. Including
200 material stock pattern indicators in Models A yields better prediction than Models B for both
201 CO₂ and TFC in terms of in-sample and out-of-sample goodness of fit, and improves the
202 Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) of model selection. Other criteria to select λ^* , and
203 alternative variable selection procedures yielded similar results (SI). Even models that
204 included only material stock pattern indicators and excluded all conventional factors
205 (including GDP) achieved good predictions (out-of-sample r^2 of 0.65 for TFC and 0.62 for
206 CO₂; see SI).

207

208 **Table 2. Multivariate analysis using cross-validation lasso.** The leftmost three columns show the lasso path
 209 for predicting cross-country patterns of TFC (above) and CO₂ (below) using all variables. In the first column λ^*
 210 denotes the optimal model (Model A) emerging from the cross-validation. CV MSPE is the cross-validated
 211 mean-square prediction error evaluated with 10-folds (for detail see Methods section). For Model B, only
 212 conventional factors are selected (lasso path not shown). The same folds are used for the assessment of all
 213 models. BIC is the Bayesian Information Criterion for model selection. r^2 is the goodness of fit within the sample
 214 of countries, and oSr^2 refers to the (cross-validated) out-of-sample goodness of fit.

215 **Models predicting TFC**

Lasso path for model A			Estimated coefficients		
λ	(A) dded, (R) emoved	CV MSPE		Model A	Model B
0.711	GDP (A)	0.703	GDP	0.494	0.572
0.371	BL _{cap} (A)	0.319	DENS	-0.017	-0.039
0.161	HDD (A), RWD _{tot} (A)	0.179	UPOP		
0.121	RD _{urb-rur} (A)	0.166	HDD	0.021	0.051
0.111	PGAS (A)	0.161	PGAS	-0.352	-0.288
0.101	RD _{urb} (A)	0.155	BL _{cap}	0.184	
0.076	RWD _{urb} (A)	0.135	BL _{mono}	-0.017	
0.063	RWD _{tot} (R)	0.125	RD _{urb}	-0.392	
0.048	DENS (A)	0.115	RL _{urb-rur}	-0.024	
0.030	BL _{mono} (R)	0.108	RD _{urb-rur}	-0.074	
0.027	RL _{urb-rur} (A)	0.107	RWD _{urb}	0.045	
0.017*	(Unchanged)	0.105	Intercept	3.457	2.542
0.016	RWD _{urb-rur} (A)	0.105			
0.013	BL _{comp} (A)	0.105			
0.011	(Unchanged)	0.106			

Measures of in-and-out-of-sample fit		
BIC	84.17	100.32
r^2	0.900	0.851
oSr^2	0.865	0.833

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217 **Models predicting CO₂**

Lasso path for model A			Estimated coefficients		
λ	(A) dded, (R) emoved	CV MSPE	Variable	Model A	Model B
0.867	GDP (A)	1.278	GDP	0.449	0.582
0.544	BL _{cap} (A)	0.801	DENS	-0.061	0.023
0.496	UPOP (A)	0.738	UPOP	0.466	0.558
0.452	RWD _{tot} (A)	0.683	HDD	0.055	0.109
0.312	HDD (A)	0.530	PGAS	-0.680	-0.688
0.215	PGAS (A)	0.446	BL _{fract}	0.201	
0.135	RD _{urb-rur} (A)	0.338	BL _{cap}	0.176	
0.123	BL _{fract} (A)	0.323	BL _{comp}	0.489	
0.085	RWL _{urb-rur} (A)	0.289	RD _{urb}	-0.201	
0.070	BL _{fract} (R)	0.280	RWD _{urb}	0.130	
0.048	BL _{comp} (A)	0.269	RWD _{rur}	0.017	
0.044	RD _{urb} (A)	0.266	Intercept	-2.723	-4.294
0.037	RWD _{urb} (A)	0.262			
0.025	BL _{fract} (A)	0.256			
0.023	DENS (A)	0.255			
0.021	RWL _{urb-rur} (R)	0.254			
0.016	RWD _{rur} (A)	0.251			
0.016	RD _{urb-rur} (R)	0.251			
0.014	RWD _{tot} (R)	0.250			
0.012*	(Unchanged)	0.249			
0.006	(Unchanged)	0.250			

Measures of in-and-out-of-sample fit		
BIC	178.44	190.82
r^2	0.873	0.812
oSr^2	0.817	0.785

218

219 **Discussion**

220 The analysis shows that extent and spatial patterns of built structures, here denoted as material
 221 stock patterns, play an important role in co-determining and predicting the level of resource

222 use, here TFC and CO₂, in a cross-country analysis. This shows that insights from urban
223 studies¹⁻⁵ generally hold at the national scale. Despite the unavoidable loss of information
224 resulting from aggregation of maps to the national scale, the indicators in Table 1 maintain
225 key information representing important characteristics of material stock patterns that strongly
226 affect cross-country patterns of TFC and CO₂. The indicators have substantial additional
227 explanatory and predictive power over conventional factors. They can help developing much
228 stronger models of national-level TFC and CO₂ than usual IPAT-type approaches, and allow
229 researchers to consider material stock patterns in analyses of a possible decoupling of
230 resource use from GDP.

231
232 Population density plays a smaller role than widely assumed, while many material stock
233 patterns strongly influence the cross-country differences in energy demand and CO₂
234 emissions. The material stock pattern indicator with the most consistent predictive power
235 across all analyses is the area of built-up land per capita (BL_{cap}), which emerges as the
236 second-most important variable (after GDP) in most of our statistical analyses. This is
237 plausible because infrastructures and buildings require energy for being built and used, which
238 results in CO₂ emissions in current fossil-fuel dominated energy systems^{34,40}. Higher BL_{cap}
239 also means larger floor size and more space between destinations, which all raises energy
240 demand in buildings and transport. These findings corroborate and expand on previous
241 analyses (that used entirely different models and did not capture spatial patterns) suggesting
242 that challenges for climate-change mitigation strongly depend on past and future
243 accumulation of material stocks in buildings and infrastructures⁴⁰⁻⁴³. This is worrying because
244 material stocks are growing globally largely in unison with GDP^{32,43}.

245
246 Our indicators and results create new options for analyzing which of the characteristics of
247 material stock patterns are most important in determining and predicting energy demand and
248 emissions. Analyses presented in Figure 2, Table 2 as well as the SI clearly show that many
249 specific aspects of material stock patterns play a role in determining cross-country differences
250 in energy demand and emissions, but the multivariate analysis also shows that these patterns
251 interact in many ways that are difficult to disentangle due to the collinearities of the material
252 stock pattern indicators.

253
254 Our results have implications for countries pursuing ambitious climate targets^{10,40}. Most
255 importantly, they show that the build-up of large, sprawling material stocks in built structures

256 is an important national-level driver of energy demand and emissions that has so far been
257 largely neglected at that level due to lacking data. Constraining land-conversion to built-up
258 land emerges as a key option of efforts towards low-energy and low-carbon futures⁴⁴ and
259 could contribute to efforts for staying within a 1.5° global heating target with limited reliance
260 on contested CO₂ reduction options such as bioenergy with carbon capture and
261 sequestration³⁵, and to reduce biodiversity loss resulting from sprawling cities⁴⁵.

262

263 *Text until here, including Abstract, excluding figures & tables: ~2400 words.*

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- 364

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377

378 **Competing interests**

379 The authors declare no competing interests

380

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385

386 **Supplementary Information and Extended Data**

387 This article includes supplementary information and Extended Data Figures.

388

389 Full data supporting this article are available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5876942>

390 Code used for calculations of maps is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5883653>

391

392 Note that one dataset exceeded the 50 GB upload limit imposed by Zenodo; this dataset will
393 be made available upon request. Both archives will be made freely available before
394 publication of the article. At present, they can be accessed by the editor and will be made
395 available for review purposes if required.

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